

THOMAS ADEWUMI UNIVERSITY
JOURNAL OF INNOVATION,
SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY (TAU-JIST)

ISSN: 3043-503X

RESEARCH ARTICLE

IMPACT OF SAGE 200 ACCOUNTING SOFTWARE ON JOB PERFORMANCE IN THE FINANCIAL SERVICES DEPARTMENT: THEMATIC AND DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

Ishola James Aransiola, Oyetola Bukunmi Oyelakun*, Oluseyanu Olamide Olayemi, and Abdul-lateef Ayomide Ibrahim

Department of Business Administration, Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Thomas Adewumi University, Oko, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Department of Accounting and Finance, Faculty of Management and Social Sciences, Thomas Adewumi University, Oko, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Corresponding Author Email:

This is an open access article distributed under the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

ARTICLE DETAILS

Article History:
 Received 02 July 2025
 Accepted 05 October 2025
 Available online 10 December 2025

ABSTRACT

This study investigates how the use of Sage 200 accounting software shapes job performance within a university's financial services department. The research focuses on the software's influence on efficiency, accuracy, and reporting quality, drawing on data collected through a semistructured questionnaire administered to ten staff members who rely on Sage 200 in their daily work. A primarily qualitative approach was adopted, using a semi-structured questionnaire to gather both narrative data for thematic analysis and categorical data for descriptive statistical summary. The findings indicate that Sage 200 contributes to faster task completion, improved accuracy in financial records, and more reliable reporting. Respondents also noted challenges, particularly limited training and occasional system disruptions, which can hinder optimal use. Overall, the study suggests that Sage 200 enhances financial operations when supported by adequate user capacity and system maintenance. The research adds to existing work on accounting software by offering a focused examination of how a specific system affects day-to-day performance in a higher-education financial services context, with implications for technology adoption in emerging economy university settings such as Nigeria, where funding constraints, infrastructure limitations, and capacity-building needs shape digital transformation outcomes.

KEYWORDS

Sage 200, Accounting Software, Financial Services, Job Performance

Introduction

Accounting remains a central component of organizational activity, providing the mechanisms through which financial transactions are recorded, monitored, and interpreted. As organizations expand and their operations become more complex, the volume and diversity of financial data have increased substantially. Manual approaches that once supported routine bookkeeping are now insufficient for handling the speed, scale, and

accuracy required in contemporary financial environments. This shift has contributed to the development and adoption of accounting software, which integrates accounting principles with technological tools to support more efficient and reliable financial management (DeStefano et al., 2023).

Globalization has further intensified the need for sophisticated accounting systems. Organizations operating across borders face new reporting requirements, heightened expectations for transparency,

Quick Response Code	Access this article online	
	<p>Website: https://journals.tau.edu.ng/index.php/tau-jist</p>	<p>DOI:</p>

Cite the Article: Ishola, J. ., Oyetola, B. O., Oluseyanu, O.O., and Abdul-lateef, A. I. (2025). Impact of Sage 200 Accounting Software on Job Performance in the Financial Services Department: Thematic and Descriptive Analysis.

and increased pressure to maintain strong internal controls. These demands have encouraged the adoption of advanced accounting software capable of supporting complex financial operations and facilitating timely decision-making (Romney & Steinbart, 2018). Within this broader technological landscape, Accounting Information Systems (AIS) such as Sage 200 have become essential components of organizational information infrastructures. AIS supports the recording, management, retrieval, and reporting of financial and non-financial information, enabling organizations to monitor resource use and strengthen decision-making processes (Abu Afifa et al., 2023).

Sage 200, in particular, has gained prominence as a tool for managing core accounting functions, including accounts receivable, accounts payable, ledger management, payroll processing, and asset tracking (Hashmicro, 2019). Its automation capabilities allow organizations to access real-time financial data, improve reporting accuracy, and streamline routine financial tasks. Prior studies highlight that AIS enhances financial control, increases data accuracy, improves cost-effectiveness, and strengthens data security, although it may also introduce challenges related to system misuse, fraud risks, and the need for continuous user training (Thottoli, 2021).

Recent technological developments have accelerated the shift toward cloud-based accounting systems. Cloud platforms offer scalability, accessibility, and flexibility, enabling organizations to manage financial information more efficiently and respond to changing operational demands (Chikkala & Jaffer, 2022; Wicaksono et al., 2020). Cloud-enabled systems such as Sage 200 allow firms to adapt quickly to market changes and leverage real-time reporting capabilities (DeStefano et al., 2023). Conversely, organizations that rely solely on traditional on-premises systems may face high maintenance costs, limited scalability, and delays in accessing critical financial data, which can hinder competitiveness in a digital environment (Chandra & Gupta, 2022; Hang et al., 2020).

The consequences of failing to adopt modern accounting technologies can be significant. Without cloud-based solutions, organizations risk operational stagnation, missed opportunities, and reduced agility in responding to market disruptions. As a result, many businesses now view cloud-based accounting systems as essential for improving efficiency, enhancing data accuracy, and supporting informed decision-making (Chikkala & Jaffer, 2022). Sage 200, in particular, reduces manual data entry, minimizes errors, and improves departmental responsiveness by enabling collaboration and real-time access to financial information.

Despite the growing body of research on accounting software, much of the existing literature focuses on organizational-level outcomes such as financial reporting quality, efficiency, and decision-making. Less attention has been given to how specific systems, such as Sage 200, shape the day-to-day job performance of employees within particular functional units. This gap is especially evident in higher-education financial services departments, where software use is integral to budgeting, reporting, reconciliation, and student-related financial processes.

Research Focus

This study examines how Sage 200 influences the work experiences of financial services staff who use the software regularly. It explores how the system affects their efficiency, accuracy, workflow, and overall job performance, providing insight into the practical implications of accounting software adoption within a university context.

Research Questions

The study is guided by the following questions:

1. What advantages does the use of Sage 200 accounting software provide in financial management?
2. What challenges do users encounter when implementing and operating Sage 200?
3. How does Sage 200 influence productivity and the accuracy of financial reporting?

Objectives of the Study

The study aims to assess the impact of Sage 200 on job performance within a financial services department. Specifically, it seeks to:

1. Identify the advantages associated with the use of Sage 200 in financial management.
2. Examine the challenges users face in implementing and operating the software.
3. Determine how Sage 200 affects productivity and the accuracy of financial reporting.

Scope of the Study

The study focuses on staff members in the Financial Services Department of Landmark University, Omu-Aran, Kwara State, Nigeria, who use Sage 200 in their daily work. It does not extend to other departments or to other accounting software used within the institution.

Significance of the Study

By examining how Sage 200 influences job performance at the operational level, this study contributes to a more detailed understanding of accounting software use in higher-education financial administration. The findings may assist financial managers, system administrators, and policymakers in improving software utilization, strengthening staff capacity, and enhancing financial management practices.

Literature Review

Theoretical Framework

This study adopts **contingency theory** as the lens for examining how Sage 200 influences job performance within a financial services department. Contingency theory argues that organizational practices,

including the design and use of accounting systems, must align with contextual conditions to be effective. Early contributions by Fiedler and later by Gordon and Miller emphasized that management practices are not universally applicable; rather, their success depends on the environment in which they operate (Gordon & Miller, 1976). Within this perspective, Accounting Information Systems (AIS) are expected to be flexible and responsive to organizational complexity, technological change, and strategic priorities.

Tiessen and Waterhouse (1983) similarly noted that technological and environmental shifts shape the structure and performance of management accounting systems. Chenhall (2003) extended this argument by highlighting that management control systems are influenced by contingency variables such as technology, organizational culture, and strategy. Langfield-Smith (1997) further observed that business strategy plays a central role in determining the nature of accounting systems adopted by organizations. Taken together, these insights suggest that the effectiveness of Sage 200 depends on how well its features align with the goals, structure, and operational realities of the financial services department. In this study, contingency theory provides a foundation for understanding why the same accounting software may produce different outcomes depending on user competence, organizational support, and contextual demands.

Empirical Review

A substantial body of research has examined the role of accounting software in improving financial reporting, operational efficiency, and organizational performance. Several studies highlight the positive contributions of AIS to data accuracy, decision-making, and internal control. For instance, Fadzilah (2017) found that efficiency, reliability, ease of use, and data quality significantly influence firm performance, emphasizing the importance of AIS for organizational sustainability. The study recommended that firms prioritize the implementation of accounting systems to enhance operational outcomes.

Research on cloud-based accounting systems has also expanded. Wicaksono et al. (2020) examined cloud accounting implementation among micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) and noted that cloud platforms improve accessibility but require strong security measures. Their findings underscore the dual nature of cloud adoption: while it enhances flexibility, it also introduces new risks that organizations must manage.

The selection of accounting software has been identified as a critical factor influencing financial reporting quality. Wickramasinghe et al. (2017) reported that poor software selection can lead to incomplete records and unauthorized access, ultimately undermining decision-making. Their work highlights the importance of aligning software capabilities with organizational needs.

In the public sector, Boateng (2019) evaluated the use of accounting software in the Ghana Education Service and found a positive relationship between software use and efficiency in financial information processing.

The study emphasized the need for staff training to ensure effective system utilization. Similarly, Jedlickova (2020) examined the impact of automated accounting software on bookkeeping roles and concluded that automation reshapes job functions, requiring new skills and continuous training.

Implementation processes also influence software effectiveness. Thompson (2020), in a project management study on Sage X3 implementation, found that structured planning aligned with Project Management Institute standards is essential for successful integration. The study recommended that organizations prioritize project management practices when adopting new accounting systems.

In higher education, Said and Aliu (2022) investigated the influence of accounting software on the qualitative characteristics of financial information in public universities in Northern Ghana. Their findings showed that efficiency, ease of use, data quality, and accuracy significantly enhance financial reporting quality. They recommended that universities invest in technology-based financial tools to strengthen reporting processes.

The relationship between software skills and job performance has also received attention. Lleshaj and Çika (2023) found that postgraduate students in finance and accounting require additional training in financial software to improve job performance. Their study suggests that educational institutions should integrate more software-based learning into their curricula.

In the Nigerian context, Nwekwo et al. (2024) reported that both ERP systems and off-the-shelf accounting software significantly improve financial reporting among corporate organizations in Southeast Nigeria. Their findings reinforce the broader consensus that accounting software enhances reporting quality. Similarly, Binuyo et al. (2024) found widespread use of computerized accounting systems among SMEs in Southwestern Nigeria and concluded that such systems support financial decision-making, recommending full computerization of accounting processes.

Emerging technologies are also reshaping financial reporting. Pandey and Rana (2024) examined AI-driven accounting software and found that artificial intelligence improves data analysis and reporting efficiency. They emphasized the importance of user-friendly software interfaces to support adoption. In a conceptual review, Sinebe and Sinebe (2024) discussed the usability of ERP and cloud accounting software, noting that digitalization reduces errors and enhances efficiency in modern business environments.

Finally, Ghanem and Al-Shammari (2024) assessed the impact of AIS on the accuracy and reliability of financial reports in the banking sector. Their findings showed a strong positive effect, demonstrating that AIS contributes significantly to organizational performance and the credibility of financial information.

Summary of Literature and Identified Gaps

Across the reviewed studies, several themes emerge. Accounting software consistently improves efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making. User competence, system selection, implementation quality, and organizational support are repeatedly identified as critical factors influencing software effectiveness. However, most existing research focuses on organizational-level outcomes or broad assessments of AIS adoption. Few studies examine how specific systems, such as Sage 200, affect the day-to-day job performance of employees within a defined functional unit.

Additionally, limited research explores the higher-education financial services context, where accounting software plays a central role in budgeting, reporting, reconciliation, and student-related financial processes. This study addresses these gaps by providing a focused examination of how Sage 200 influences job performance within a university financial services department.

Methodology

Study Area

The study was conducted in the Financial Services Department at Landmark University, Omu-Aran, Kwara State, Nigeria. The localized scope of the study guarantees the research findings are directly relevant to the participants and the study environment, and it becomes more convenient to create actionable insights into how Sage 200 accounting software influences job performance in financial services.

Research Design

A survey research design is employed in this study, as it is the most suitable method for capturing data directly from participants who may have a bearing on instituting an impact of Sage 200 accounting software within finance departments. Under this design, data about users' experiences, perceptions, and opinions were captured.

More specifically, this study adopts an exploratory, qualitative-rich single-case study design aimed at achieving analytical generalization rather than statistical generalization. In line with established case study methodology (Yin, 2018), the objective is not to generalize findings to a broader population statistically, but to extend and refine theoretical understanding, particularly contingency theory, within a clearly bounded organizational context. The in-depth examination of a single financial services department allows for contextualized insight into how accounting software effectiveness is contingent upon organizational conditions such as user competence, support structures, and infrastructure stability.

Population of the Study

The study applies to accountants in the Financial Services Department of Landmark University. It encompasses the whole population because their total is ten, making it possible to include all. Including all ten accountants in the study gave a comprehensive understanding of the software impact

concerning every individual's opinion that makes up the outcome. It also ensures that sampling bias is eliminated and renders the research results more credible as well as usable.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

This study sampled ten accountants who serve in the Financial Services Department for that entire population. Selection of participants was done based on the purposive sampling method. This is because it is appropriate for selecting participants who have personal experience applying Sage 200 Enterprise accounting software for work. Purposive sampling ensures that the respondents possess the necessary experience and expertise to provide meaningful insights into the benefits, challenges, and overall impact of the software on their work performance.

Type of Data

Both primary qualitative and quantitative data were utilized during the study to strike a balance in the analysis of the research problem. The quantitative data is an objective measurement in the context of the use of Sage 200 accounting software. Qualitative data captures subjective thoughts and views of participants and creates an extended contextual consciousness.

However, the study is primarily qualitatively driven, with quantitative elements serving a descriptive and supportive role. The integration of open-ended responses for thematic interpretation alongside frequency-based summaries enhances depth without constituting a fully integrated mixed-methods inference design.

Data Gathering Method

Qualitative and quantitative data were collected from the target respondents through a semi-structured paper-based survey questionnaire. The questionnaire, structured with relevant questions, both open- and closed-ended, helps to capture qualitative information along with some quantitative data about the research objectives. The questionnaire also underwent validation by expert review.

Ethical Considerations

The study strictly adheres to ethical principles with the objective to ensure that the rights and dignity of the participants are protected. The aim, extent, and possible implications of the study were explained to potential participants so as to foster voluntary and informed participation. Respondents' identities and their responses are kept confidential to assure confidentiality and protection of privacy.

Method of Data Analysis

Descriptive and thematic analyses were performed. This descriptive analysis helps to find patterns or trends in the responses received from the participants and communicate the results using frequency and percentage. Thematic analysis, on the other hand, involves

categorization of the qualitative data into themes for the purpose of getting similar problems, benefits, and effects of Sage 200 accounting software. These two methods have been said to give a detailed analysis of numeric and narrative data.

In line with the exploratory case study orientation, thematic analysis served as the primary analytical strategy, enabling pattern identification and conceptual linkage among themes. Descriptive statistics (frequencies and percentages) were used to summarize categorical responses, thereby supporting interpretation rather than driving causal inference.

Results

Table 1: Thematic Analysis of Response to Survey Question 1 on Participant Roles & Responsibilities

Theme	Participant	Role Title	Major Responsibilities
Core Accounting & Bookkeeping	P1	Accounting Officer	General bookkeeping, accounting, and reporting
			Payment vouchers, cheque/instruction preparation, record-keeping, Sage 200 postings, cash retirement
Reconciliation & Final Accounts	P2	Final Account Officer (Reconciliation)	Reconcile general and sub-ledgers, detect posting errors
			Reconciliation of all school accounts
Budgeting & Financial Oversight	P4	Head of Financial Operations	Budget coordination, revenue management, financial oversight, reporting, strategic alignment
			Final Account Officer
	P3	Expenditure Officer	
	P5		

	P8	Unit Reviewer	Reviewing operations, batch processing, journal entries, reports and budget preparation
	P9	Finance & Budgeting Officer	Financial planning and budgeting (general description)
Student-Facing Financial	P6	Student Account Officer	Student clearance, financial status support, handling withdrawal requests
Data Management & Systems	P7	EDP Officer	Data integrity, financial database oversight, anomaly detection, reporting using Sage 200
Investment & Treasury Functions	P10	Investment Accountant	Investment booking and liquidation, liaising with banks on investment matters

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

Table 1 shows the distribution of staff roles and responsibilities, highlighting how Sage 200 users contribute to core accounting, reconciliation, budgeting, student finance, data management, and investment functions within the department.

Table 2: Percentage Distribution of Socio-Demographic Information of Respondents

Survey Question Number	Question	Category	Frequency (N = 10)	Percentage (%)
2	Experience with Sage 200	Less than 1 year	0	0
		1–3 years	7	70
		4–6 years	0	0
		More than 6 years	3	30
		Total	10	100
3	Financial Department Size	1–5 employees	0	0
		6–10 employees	5	50
		11–20 employees	3	30
		More than 20 employees	2	20
		Total	10	100

4	Financial Services Provided	Accounting and Bookkeeping	1	10
		Financial Analysis & Reporting	6	60
		Payroll and Tax Management	0	0
		Other	3	30
		Total	10	100
5	Industry Type	Banking	0	0
		Insurance	0	0
		Investment	0	0
		Higher Education	10	100
		Total	10	100

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

Table 2 summarizes respondents’ experience levels, department size, service areas, and sector classification, indicating most users have 1–3 years of Sage 200 experience and work in medium-sized higher-education financial units.

Table 3: Thematic Analysis of Response to Survey Question 6 on Benefits of Sage 200 (Research Objective 1)

Theme	Frequency	Participant(s)	Sub-Themes
Time-Saving & Efficiency	4	P1, P2, P5, P6	“Saves time”, “Reduces time spent on reports”, “Reduces time wastage”, “Quick processing of data”
Accuracy in Reporting	3	P3, P4, P5	“Provides accurate and timely financial report”, “Accuracy in report generation”
Error Detection & Accountability	3	P1, P2, P6	“Helps to trace wrong postings”, “Detect errors immediately”, “Improves accountability”
Improved Record Management	1	P2	“Aids in looking for file when missing”

Smooth Chart of Accounts Handling	1	P3	“Chart of account goes smoothly”
Real-time Operation Capability	1	P6	“Facilitates operating at a point in time”
Inventory Management Improvement	1	P4	“Improvement in inventory”

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

Table 3 identifies key perceived benefits of Sage 200, including time-saving, improved accuracy, error detection, better record management, smoother chart-of-accounts handling, real-time operations, and enhanced inventory management.

Table 4: Percentage Distribution of Advantages of Sage 200 in Financial Management (Research Objective 1)

Survey Question Number	Variables	Category	Frequency (N = 10)	Percentage (%)
7	Automation Capability of Sage 200	Very Poor	0	0
		Poor	1	10
		Neutral	2	20
		Good	5	50
		Very Good	2	20
		Total	10	100
8	Timeliness & Accuracy of Insights	Yes, always	6	60
		Yes, sometimes	3	30
		Rarely	1	10
		Never	0	0
		Total	10	100
9	Multi-Currency Effectiveness	Not Applicable	2	20
		Not Effective	2	20
		Somewhat Effective	2	20
		Very Effective	4	40
		Total	10	100
10	Integration with Other Systems	Not at all	1	10

	Poorly	2	20
	Moderately	3	30
	Very well	4	40
	Total	10	100

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

Table 4 presents respondents’ ratings of Sage 200 advantages, showing strong approval of automation, timeliness, accuracy, multi-currency handling, and system integration, with most users reporting positive performance outcomes.

Table 5: Thematic Analysis of Response to Survey Question 11 on Challenges of Sage 200 Implementation (Research Objective 2)

Theme	Frequency	Participant(s)	Sub-Themes
Cost and Affordability	3	P1, P5, P9	“Somehow expensive”, “Expensive to manage”, “Too costly for a small department”
Need for User Training	3	P1, P5, P7	“Requires training before use”, “It’s complex”, “Staff need orientation before using it effectively”
Data Migration Difficulties	4	P3, P4, P6, P8	“Data migration issues”, “Could not migrate payroll and budget”, “Transfer of old data was difficult”
System Complexity	3	P5, P7, P10	“It is complex”, “Too many features make it hard to navigate”, “Non-intuitive interface”
Integration Issues	2	P2, P6	“Hard transferring items”, “Does not integrate well with our HR software”
Upgrade/Maintenance Burden	2	P1, P10	“Update of the software”, “Frequent updates disrupt our flow”

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

Table 5 highlights major challenges encountered with Sage 200, including high costs, training needs, data-migration issues, system complexity, integration problems, and maintenance burdens.

Table 6: Percentage Distribution of Challenges of Implementing Sage 200 (Research Objective 2)

Survey Question Number	Variables	Category	Frequency (N = 10)	Percentage (%)
12	Learning Difficulty of Sage 200	Very Difficult	1	10
		Difficult	2	20
		Moderate	2	20
		Easy	5	50
		Very Easy	0	0
	Total		10	100
13	Data Migration Issues Experienced	Yes, many issues	2	20
		Yes, some issues	4	40
		No issues	3	30
		Not Applicable	1	10
		Total	10	100
14	Satisfaction with Sage 200 Support	Very Dissatisfied	2	20
		Dissatisfied	2	20
		Neutral	2	20
		Satisfied	3	30
		Very Satisfied	1	10
		Total	10	100
15	Customization Options Available	Very Limited	1	10
		Limited	2	20
		Moderate	3	30
		Extensive	4	40
		Total	10	100

Source: Author’s Computation, 2025

Table 6 shows the frequency of challenges experienced, indicating moderate learning difficulty, common data-migration issues, mixed satisfaction with support services, and varying perceptions of customization options.

Table 7: Thematic Analysis of Response to Survey Question 16 on Impact of Sage 200 on Productivity and Accuracy (Research Objective 3)

Theme	Frequency	Participant (s)	Representative Quotes
Improved Productivity & Time-Saving	5	P1, P3, P5, P6, P8	"It aids productivity and ease time factor", "Reduces time on reporting", "Saves time"
Increased Accuracy in Reporting	4	P3, P4, P5, P7	"Increases confidence in report presentation", "Improved financial reports", "Accuracy of results improved"
Efficient Report Generation	4	P3, P4, P6, P9	"Efficiency of monthly closing", "Improved record keeping", "Accommodates bulk transactions"
Enhanced Usability	3	P1, P5, P9	"Easy to learn and understand", "User-friendly interface", "Straightforward layout"
Capacity to Handle Large Data Volumes	4	P1, P5, P6, P10	"Accommodates a lot of transactions", "Processes many data within short time"
Resource Optimization	2	P6, P7	"Reduces manpower", "Reduces duplicate tasks"

Source: Author's Computation, 2025

Table 7 summarizes thematic insights on productivity and accuracy, showing improvements in efficiency, reporting accuracy, usability, data-handling capacity, and resource optimization attributed to Sage 200.

Table 8: Percentage Distribution of Impact on Productivity and Accuracy of Financial Reporting (Research Objective 3)

Survey Question Number	Variables	Category	Frequency (N = 10)	Percentage (%)
17	Time to Generate Reports	Significantly Reduced	7	70
		Somewhat Reduced	1	10
		No Change	0	0
		Increased	1	10
		Total	10	100
18	Accuracy of Reports	Very Inaccurate	0	0
		Inaccurate	0	0
		Neutral	1	10
		Accurate	3	30
		Very Accurate	6	60
Total	10	100		
19	Month-End Closing Process Improvement	Yes, significantly	8	80
		Yes, moderately	2	20
		No Change	0	0
		Not Applicable	0	0

		Total	10	100
20	Audit Trail Confidence	Not at all	0	0
		Slightly	0	0
		Moderately	4	40
		Very much	6	60
		Total	10	100

Source: Author's Computation, 2025

Table 8 illustrates respondents' overall assessment of Sage 200's impact on productivity and reporting accuracy, confirming strong positive effects across key performance indicators.

Discussion of Results

The findings of this study show that Sage 200 plays a meaningful role in shaping job performance within the university's financial services department. Respondents consistently described improvements in efficiency, accuracy, and reporting quality, which aligns with broader evidence that accounting software enhances operational performance and strengthens financial information systems (Fadzilah, 2017; Said & Aliu, 2022). However, beyond identifying these improvements, the findings reveal that performance gains are not automatic outcomes of software adoption. Rather, they emerge through the interaction between system capabilities, user competence, and organizational support structures. The discussion below interprets these findings by explicitly connecting benefits and challenges within a structured analytical narrative.

Efficiency and Accuracy in Financial Tasks

Participants reported that Sage 200 reduces the time required to complete routine financial tasks and minimizes manual errors. These observations are consistent with earlier studies showing that accounting software improves the speed and reliability of financial processing (Boateng, 2019; Binuyo et al., 2024). The automated features of Sage 200, such as real-time ledger updates and built-in reconciliation tools, appear to support staff in managing workloads more effectively and reinforce operational efficiency.

However, the improvement in efficiency is closely tied to users' familiarity with the system. Staff members who reported stronger competence in using Sage 200 described greater time savings and smoother task execution. This suggests that automation alone does not guarantee productivity; rather, user capacity mediates the extent to which automation translates into performance gains. Where training gaps exist, efficiency improvements may be uneven across users. The emphasis on accuracy also reflects findings from research on AIS adoption, which highlights the role of digital systems in strengthening internal controls and reducing the likelihood of human error (Nwekwo et al., 2024). Respondents' experiences suggest that Sage 200 contributes to a more dependable financial reporting environment, particularly when users are familiar with its core functions. Thus, efficiency and accuracy are interconnected outcomes, both dependent on the effective utilization of system features.

Reporting Quality and Decision Making

The study found that Sage 200 enhances reporting quality by generating standardized, easily interpretable financial reports. This aligns with research showing that accounting software improves the clarity and reliability of financial information, thereby supporting better decision-making (Said & Aliu, 2022; Ghanem & Al Shammari, 2024). Respondents noted that the system's reporting tools help them respond more quickly to internal information requests, strengthening departmental coordination and responsiveness.

Importantly, improved reporting quality appears to be a downstream outcome of enhanced efficiency and accuracy. When transactions are processed accurately and reconciliations are performed promptly, the resulting reports are more reliable and easier to interpret. In this sense, reporting quality is not an isolated benefit but the cumulative result of improved data entry processes, system automation, and effective internal controls.

These findings reinforce the argument that AIS contributes not only to operational efficiency but also to strategic decision-making by providing timely and accurate financial insights (Wicaksono et al., 2020). In a university financial services context where budgeting, reconciliation, and compliance-related tasks are routine, the ability to generate reliable reports quickly enhances administrative responsiveness and institutional accountability.

Challenges Limiting Optimal System Use

Despite the benefits, respondents identified challenges that limit the full realization of Sage 200's capabilities. The most prominent issue was insufficient training, which left some staff uncertain about advanced features and troubleshooting procedures. This aligns with studies emphasizing the importance of user competence in maximizing the value of accounting software (Jedlickova, 2020; Lleshaj & Çika, 2023).

The relationship between training and usability is particularly significant. While some respondents described the system as user-friendly, others highlighted its complexity. This variation suggests that perceived usability is not solely a feature of system design but also a function of user preparedness. Adequate training appears to transform system complexity into usability, while insufficient training amplifies perceived difficulty.

Similarly, occasional system disruptions were identified as constraints. Although not frequent, such interruptions can disrupt time-sensitive financial operations. As Thompson (2020) noted, system reliability and implementation quality significantly influence user satisfaction and performance. Even minor disruptions may reduce confidence in the system, thereby weakening the consistency of efficiency and accuracy gains.

Taken together, the challenges identified as training gaps, system complexity, and technical disruptions suggest that the realization of Sage 200's benefits depends on a supportive organizational environment. Without structured capacity building and reliable

technical infrastructure, performance improvements may be uneven or partially constrained.

Interpreting the Findings through Contingency Theory

Contingency theory provides a useful lens for understanding why Sage 200 produces positive outcomes in some areas while facing limitations in others. The theory argues that the effectiveness of an information system depends on its alignment with organizational context, including user skills, workflow design, and technological support (Chenhall, 2003; Gordon & Miller, 1976).

In this study, Sage 200 aligns well with the department's operational needs for efficiency, accuracy, and reliable reporting. However, the presence of training gaps and occasional system disruptions indicates areas where contextual alignment is weaker. These findings suggest that software impact is conditional rather than automatic.

The evidence supports a structured performance pathway:

Training and Technical Support → Enhanced Usability and System Confidence → Improved Efficiency and Accuracy → Higher Reporting Quality → Enhanced Job Performance

Where the initial conditions, training, and reliable support are strong, positive outcomes cascade through subsequent stages. Where these conditions are weak, system complexity and disruptions may interrupt the performance pathway.

This reinforces the broader argument in AIS research that technology alone does not guarantee improved performance; organizational support and user readiness are equally important (Tiessen & Waterhouse, 1983; Langfield-Smith, 1997). Sage 200's effectiveness, therefore, is contingent upon the alignment between technological capability and organizational capacity.

Contribution to Existing Knowledge

This study contributes to the literature by offering a focused examination of Sage 200 within a higher education financial services context, an area that has received limited attention. While many studies examine AIS adoption in corporate or public sector settings, fewer explore how specific systems influence day-to-day performance in university administrative units.

More importantly, the study moves beyond listing benefits and challenges to demonstrate how they interact. By explicitly linking training, usability, efficiency, accuracy, and reporting quality within a conditional framework, the findings provide a more nuanced understanding of how accounting software shapes job performance. This integrative perspective extends prior research by showing that software success is not simply a matter of technological sophistication but of organizational alignment and capacity development within sector-specific contexts.

Conclusion

This study examined the impact of Sage 200 accounting software on job performance within the Financial Services Department of a higher education

institution. The findings demonstrate that Sage 200 significantly enhances efficiency, accuracy, and workflow coordination, enabling staff to complete tasks more quickly, maintain accurate records, and generate reliable financial reports. These improvements support the principles of contingency theory, which emphasize the importance of aligning information systems with organizational needs and operational environments.

Despite these benefits, the study also identified challenges such as system complexity, data migration difficulties, limited training, and inconsistent technical support. These issues highlight the need for continuous capacity building, structured implementation planning, and improved system optimization to ensure that users can fully leverage the capabilities of Sage 200.

Theoretical implications: The study reinforces contingency theory by demonstrating that the effectiveness of accounting software depends on organizational context, user competence, and system support. It also contributes to AIS literature by providing evidence from a higher education financial environment.

Practical implications: Organizations should invest in regular training, strengthen technical support structures, and ensure proper data migration planning. These measures will enhance user proficiency and maximize the benefits of Sage 200.

Policy implications: Higher education institutions should adopt policies that support digital transformation, continuous staff development, and system integration across departments.

Limitations: The study is limited by its small sample size and single-institution focus, which may affect generalizability.

Future research: Further studies could compare Sage 200 with other accounting systems, explore cross-institutional differences, or conduct longitudinal assessments of software impact over time.

Recommendations

Based on the study findings, the following are recommended:

1. The organization must allow an open and continuing training of its staff to gain user skills, especially for new users on the interface and its features of Sage 200.
2. Upscaling customer support systems to fast technical help, onboarding support, and user guides on various expertise levels must be provided by service providers and software vendors to increase customer satisfaction.
3. Phased implementation of Sage 200, starting with essentials and expanding gradually should minimize the chances of electronic migration errors or loss of system time.
4. An internal team of skilled professionals conducts day-to-day system problem solving, routine maintenance, and

configurations for less dependency on consulting services externally.

5. Budgeting, reconciliation, and reporting customized towards needs can be worked on with the help of an IT analyst or consultant providing resources.
6. Periodical evaluation of the systems would enable the institutions to realize the gaps in use, track the benefits, and suggest improvements towards increasing operational efficiency.
7. The organizations should set up feedback mechanisms to enable users to share their usage experience, report failure events, and provide suggestions on any improvement.

References

- Abu Afifa, M. M., Vo Van, H., & Le Hoang Van, T. (2023). Blockchain adoption in accounting by an extended UTAUT model: Empirical evidence from an emerging economy. *Journal of Financial Reporting and Accounting*, 21(1), 5–44. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JFRA-12-2021-0434>
- Binuyo, G., Olaposi, T., & Ige, Z. (2024). Computerized accounting system as an aid to effective financial reporting in small and medium scale food and beverage firms in Southwestern Nigeria. *African Journal of Science Policy and Innovation Management*, 3(1), 84–93.
- Boateng, C. (2019). *Evaluating the impact of the use of accounting software on the processing of financial information: A case of Ghana Education Service, New Juaben Municipality* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Cape Coast). <https://ir.ucc.edu.gh>
- Chandra, P., & Gupta, A. (2022). Transformation of conventional to digital accounting: An overview of cloud accounting. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*, 9, Article eISSN-2349-5162.
- Chenhall, R. H. (2003). Management control systems design within its organizational context: Findings from contingency-based research and directions for the future. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 28(2–3), 127–168. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-3682\(01\)00027-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-3682(01)00027-7)
- Chikkala, R., & Jaffer, S. (2022). Cloud accounting as a new business model. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 28(4), 723–731.
- Davis, F. D. (1989). Perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, and user acceptance of information technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13(3), 319–340. <https://doi.org/10.2307/249008>
- DeStefano, T., Kneller, R., & Timmis, J. (2023). Cloud computing and firm growth. *Review of Economics and Statistics*, 105(1), 1–17. <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3618829>
- Donaldson, L. (1999). *Performance-driven organizational change: The organizational portfolio*. Sage Publications.
- Fadzilah, N. S. (2017). The impact of accounting software on business performance. *International Journal of Accounting & Business Management*, 5(1), 1–7.
- Fiedler, F. E. (1964). A contingency model of leadership effectiveness. *Advances in Experimental Social Psychology*, 1, 149–190. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601\(08\)60051-9](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0065-2601(08)60051-9)
- Ghanem, M. B., & Al-Shammari, A. J. (2024). The impact of accounting information systems on ensuring the accuracy and reliability of financial reports. In *ZAC Conference Series: Social Sciences and Humanities*, 1(1), 125–136.
- Gordon, L. A., & Miller, D. (1976). A contingency framework for the design of accounting information systems. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 1(1), 59–69. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682\(76\)90007-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682(76)90007-6)
- Gordon, L. A., & Narayanan, V. K. (1984). Management accounting systems, perceived environmental uncertainty and organization structure: An empirical investigation. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 9(1), 33–47. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682\(84\)90028-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0361-3682(84)90028-X)
- Hang, N. T. T., Hai, V. T., Trung, T. Q., Chien, V. M., & Nga, N. T. H. (2020). Factors affecting the capacity of accounting software in controlling frauds and errors in SMEs: A case study of SMEs in Hanoi, Vietnam. *Vietnam Journal of Agricultural Science*, 3(3), 746–755.
- Hashmicro. (2019). The importance of accounting software for businesses. In Kanya (Ed.), *Businesses Tech: ERP and business management blog*. <https://www.hashmicro.com>
- Hla, D., & Teru, S. P. (2015). Efficiency of accounting information system and performance measures. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary and Current Research*, 3(2), 976–984.
- Hofer, C. W. (1975). Toward a contingency theory of business strategy. *Academy of Management Journal*, 18(4), 784–810. <https://doi.org/10.5465/255379>
- Hurt, R. L. (2013). *Accounting information systems: Basic concepts and current issues* (3rd ed.). McGraw-Hill Education.
- Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria. (2014). *Financial reporting and ethics*. ICAN Study Pack.
- Jedlickova, K. (2020). *Impact of automated accounting software on bookkeeping jobs*.
- Jensen, M. C., & Meckling, W. H. (1976). Theory of the firm: Managerial behavior, agency costs and ownership structure. *Journal of Financial Economics*, 3(4), 305–360. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X\(76\)90026-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/0304-405X(76)90026-X)
- Langfield-Smith, K. (1997). Management control systems and strategy: A critical review. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 22(2), 207–232. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-3682\(95\)00040-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0361-3682(95)00040-2)

- Lleshaj, L., & Çika, N. (2023). Software skills and their impact on enhancing job performance: A perspective from finance and accounting postgraduate students. *Review of Economics and Finance*, 21, 2485–2493.
- Nwekwo, N. M., Anisiuba, C., Eneh, S. N., Chukwuani, V., & Ugwu, N. (2024). Effects of accounting software on the financial reporting of corporate organizations in Southeast Nigeria. *Journal of Business Research and Practice*, 36(2), 142–153.
- Pandey, S. K., & Rana, N. S. (2024). Automatic financial report using accounting software based on artificial intelligence. *Journal of Lifestyle and SDGs Review*, 4(4), e03619.
- Rahman, N. A. A., Melewar, T. C., Foroudi, P., & Gupta, S. (2024). The role of technology advancement in managing business and establishing corporate brand image: Conception, challenges, and commendation in logistics and transport sector. In *Corporate branding in logistics and transportation* (pp. 26–41). Routledge.
- Romney, M. B., & Steinbart, P. J. (2017). *Accounting information systems* (14th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Romney, M. B., & Steinbart, P. J. (2018). *Accounting information systems* (15th ed.). Pearson Education.
- Said, Y. I., & Aliu, A. A. (2022). The influence of accounting software on achieving the IASB's qualitative characteristics of financial information in public universities in Northern Ghana. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 10, 26–38.
- Sinebe, M., & Sinebe, H. (2024). Conceptual review of some accounting computer softwares and its usability in the 21st century business environment.
- Thompson, I. J. (2020). *Project management plan for the implementation of Sage X3 accounting software at the Development Finance Corporation, Belmopan, Belize, CA* (Doctoral dissertation, Universidad Para La Cooperación Internacional).
- Ingittoli, M. M. (2021). Knowledge and use of accounting software: Evidence from Oman. *Journal of Industry–University Collaboration*, 3(1), 5–15. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jiuc-04-2020-0005>
- Tiessen, P., & Waterhouse, J. H. (1983). Towards a descriptive theory of management accounting. *Accounting, Organizations and Society*, 8(2–3), 251–267. <https://ideas.repec.org/a/eee/aosoci/v8y1983i2-3p251-267.html>
- Wickramasinghe, D. M. J., Pamarathna, R. M. M. D., Cooray, N. H. K., & Dissanayake, T. D. S. H. (2017). Impact of accounting software for business performance. *Imperial Journal of Interdisciplinary Research*, 3(5), 1–6.
- Wicaksono, A., Kartikasary, M., & Salma, N. (2020). Analyze cloud accounting software implementation and security system for accounting in MSMEs and cloud accounting software developer. In *Proceedings of the 2020 International Conference on Information Management and Technology (ICIMTech)* (pp. 538–543). IEEE. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICIMTech50083.2020.9211271>
- Yin, R. K. (2018). *Case study research and applications: Design and methods* (6th ed.). SAGE Publications. https://www.scirp.org/reference/referencespapers?reference_id=2914980

